

Optimization of the Short-Cut Enhanced Nutrient Abatement (SCENA) system using fermented cellulosic primary sludge as carbon source

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Introduction

Anaerobic sewage sludge digestion results in the release of soluble organic nitrogen-containing compounds, ammonium and orthophosphate from the sludge mass into the bulk liquid, so that the reject water generated by the dewatering of the digested sludge has elevated nutrients concentrations. This nutrient rich stream is commonly recycled to the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) influent or directly to secondary biological treatment, resulting in increased nutrient loadings to the mainstream wastewater treatment processes. Although the sidestream accounts for only about 1 % of daily average influent flow, it can increase the nitrogen load to the mainstream biological treatment by 20-25 % (Inc. Metcalf & Eddy, 2014) and the phosphorus loading by up to 40-65% in case of application of mainstream BioP processes (Destison, 2006). The sidestream inflow may lead to an increase in air supply, and thus the energy demand, and chemical requirements for biological nutrient removal (BNR) processes. To minimize these negative impacts and reduce plant operating costs in terms of energy, chemicals and maintenance, the reject water from anaerobic digester should be treated separately before it is recycled to the headworks of the WWTPs. Short-cut nitrogen removal (SCNR) through the ammonium oxidation to nitrite and its subsequent reduction to gaseous nitrogen has gained increasing attention over the last years. The completely autotrophic nitrogen removal process is considered more economically attractive as it further reduces energy demand and has no external carbon source requirements. However, its operational and environmental sensitivity, especially to variability and shock loadings, and the facts that neither enhanced biological phosphorus removal can be achieved nor nitrogen is completely removed are major concerns for its wide implementation (Malamis et al., 2014). On the other hand, SCNR can be conveniently coupled with suitable bioprocesses for phosphorus removal through its accumulation in biomass and can be a sustainable option resulting in the production of high added value products. In fact, the mechanism of phosphorus uptake can be realized under aerobic and anoxic conditions by phosphorus accumulating organisms (PAOs) that can utilize oxygen and/or nitrite as electron acceptors (Carvalho et al., 2007), which compete with glycogen accumulating organisms (GAOs) for the available carbon source. Indeed, to achieve an effective nitrogen and phosphorus removal via-nitrite, readily biodegradable COD should be provided and cellulosic primary sludge from sieved municipal wastewater (Ruiken et al., 2013) represents a valuable substrate to produce Volatile Fatty Acids (VFAs) by acidogenic fermentation. In this work, the enrichment of PAOs from activated sludge were carried out in a lab scale Sequencing Batch Reactor (SBR) using the fermentation liquid from cellulosic primary sludge for nitrogen and phosphorus removal from anaerobic

supernatant. Moreover, the competition between PAOs and GAOs were deeply investigated by FISH analyses.

Material and Methods

Production of VFAs from cellulosic primary sludge

The fermentation of cellulosic primary sludge (CPS) was carried out at mesophilic conditions (37°C) in a Sequencing Batch Fermentation Reactor (SBFR) with a working volume of 4 liters. The hydraulic retention time (HRT) was maintained at 3 days. The resulted fermentation liquid after S/L separation was stored in a 25 L of tank and then used as carbon source for the SBR. VFAs composition of cellulosic sludge fermentation liquid was examined, as reported in the table below.

Table 1.1. VFAs concentration and compositions in the fermentation liquid of cellulosic sludge

Type of acid	Units	Value Average±st.dev	Percentage (%)
HAc	mgCOD/L	4255	58
HPr	mgCOD/L	2003	27
HBut	mgCOD/L	984	14
Other SCFAs	mgCOD/L	-	<1
Total	mgCOD/L	7242	100

Cations concentration were investigated and an average value of about 61, 50 and 103mg L⁻¹ was detected for K⁺, Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺, respectively.

The short-cut Sequencing Batch Reactor

The lab-scale SBR (scSBR) had a working volume of 28 liters and it was inoculated with thickened WAS of Carbonera WWTP. The length of the cycles were controlled by a PLC (SIMATIC S7-1200; Siemens) and each phase were monitored through submerged probes like conductivity (3798S sc; Hach-Lange) and oxygen (LDO; Hach-lange). The oxygen concentration during the aerobic phase was kept at a concentration range of 1.5-2.5 mgO₂ L⁻¹. The whole experimental periods (around 100 days) involved two main period: 1) PAOs enrichments, where the SBR alternated anaerobic and aerobic phases; 2) Short-Cut EBPR, where the SBR accomplished anaerobic, aerobic and anoxic phases. At the beginning of the latter period, acclimatized biomass for the via-nitrite ammonia oxidation was added to the resulted enriched PAOs biomass at the period 1 and the cycle was set up according with Frison et al., 2016.

The operating conditions of the two stages were reported in table

Table 1.2 Operating conditions of the SBR during period 1 and period 2.

Parameter	Period 1	Period 2
	PAOs Enrichment	Short-Cut EBPR
Total vNLR applied (kgN m ⁻³ d ⁻¹)	-	0.55 (0.42-0.64)
vPLR applied (gP m ⁻³ d ⁻¹)	32.9 (28.35-38.7)	41 (31.9-51.7)

vOLR applied (kgCOD m ⁻³ d ⁻¹)	0.52	1.77 (1.64-1.89)
MLSS (kg m ⁻³)	2.9 (2.6-3.1)	5.9 (4.7-6.9)
MLVSS (kg m ⁻³)	2.2 (1.9-2.4)	4.7 (3.8-5.7)
SRT	8	12

The cold perchloric acid methods extraction (Haas et al., 2000) were performed in the final biomass to evaluate the forms of the phosphorus removed from the anaerobic supernatant.

Results and discussions

PAOs enrichment using fermented cellulosic primary sludge

Figure 1.1(a) shows the typical profiles obtained during the period 1 dedicated to the enrichment of PAOs. During the anaerobic phase, the VFAs from the cellulosic sludge were uptaken by the biomass according with 30-40 mgCOD gVSS⁻¹h⁻¹.

Figure 1.1. (a) Profile of VFAs and phosphate during the period for PAOs enrichment; (b) Profile of the VFAs, nitrogen and phosphate during the period for Short-Cut EBPR

As a consequence of the VFA uptake, around 35 mgP/L were released during the first 60 minutes of anaerobic phase and then stabilized at around 40 mgP L⁻¹. During the aerobic phase, the uptake of PO₄-P was observed with a maximal rate of 10.9 mgCOD gVSS⁻¹h⁻¹ (Table 1.3), which is considered a good P bioremoval activity by Janssen et al., 2002. The VFAs produced by the cellulosic primary sludge were suitable to establish a stable and effective enhanced bio-P removal process. In period 2, although the bio-P removal capacity was maintained, the sPRR and the sPUR decreased to 3.7 and 4.7 mgCOD gVSS⁻¹h⁻¹ respectively.

Table 1.3 Kinetics and operating parameters obtained

Parameter	PAOs Enrichment (45 days)	Short-Cut EBPR (45 days)
	Average ±st.dev	Average ±st.dev
Electron acceptor	Oxygen	Oxygen/Nitrite
Carbon source	Cellulosic Primary sludge	Cellulosic Primary sludge
sPRR (mgP gVSS ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	13.4±0.8	3.3±1.4

sPUR _{aerobic} (mgP gVSS ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	10.9±0.4	4.7±1.9
sPUR _{anoxic} (mgP gVSS ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	-	1.62±1.1
sVFA uptake rate _{anaerobic} (mgCOD gVSS ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	30.6±15.7	13.41±4
sNUR (mgN gVSS ⁻¹ h ⁻¹)	-	34.69±4.9
sPUR/sNUR (mgP mgN ⁻¹)	-	0.05±0.03
sPRR/sVFA uptake rate (mgP mgCOD ⁻¹)	0.34± 0.05	0.29±0.06

Indeed, many authors reported that PAOs bacteria could be partial inhibited at certain level of nitrite and mainly under aerobic conditions (Saito et al., 2004). Moreover, the observed ratio sPRR/VFA uptaken of 0.29 mgP mgCOD⁻¹, which is higher than period 1, indicated an “intermediate” metabolism due to the competition between PAOs and GAOs as reported by Saad et al., 2016. The phosphorus removed, mainly under aerobic conditions, was stored in the biomass cell up to obtain a final concentration of 57mgP gTS⁻¹. The cold perchloric acid methods revealed that only 8 mgP gTS⁻¹ was P chemically-bounded, while almost all was removed biologically.

FISH analyses

Figure 1.2 shows the link between the presence of PAOs bacteria detected by 40 FISH images using PAOmix and GAOmix as probe. During both periods, the increase of the release and the uptake rates of phosphorus is related with the increase of presence of PAOs in the biomass. In period 1, the presence of PAOs was the highest and achieving around 50%, which is in accordance with previous studies (Ohemen et al., 2004).

Table 1.2 Link between the release and uptake rates of phosphorus with the presence of PAOs

On the other hand, the period 1 shows the minimal presence of GAOs (Figure 1.3), which confirmed that the fermented cellulosic primary sludge is suitable to obtain an effective biological phosphorus removal.

However, in period 2 the presence of PAOs decrease up to 20%, probably due to the increase of the competition between PAOs and GAOs bacteria which is in agreement with the observed performances during the lab scale experiments.

Table 1.3 Presence of PAOs and GAOs during period 1 and period 2

Conclusions

The Short-Cut EBPR was validated at lab scale SBR using VFAs derived from the fermentation of cellulosic primary sludge for the treatment of anaerobic supernatant. The results of the experiments pointed out that phosphorus could be uptaken at high rate in the biomass cell under aerobic and anoxic conditions. The phosphorus concentration in the biomass cell achieved 57 mgP gTS^{-1} , where around 14% was phosphorus precipitated and thus chemically-bounded. The presence of high level of nitrite might partially inhibits the activity of PAOs bacteria if not acclimatized. On the other hands, the ratio sPRR/VFAs was an effective indicator of the competition between PAOs/GAOs, which was then confirmed by the FISH analyses. The latter showed that the presence of PAOs decreased from around 50% to 20% when the short-cut EBPR was established, probably due to the increase of presence of GAOs.

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